

BIOREMEDIATION OF DIFFERENT WASTE WATERS – A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Bioremediation of different waste waters is a relatively new technology that has undergone more intense investigation in recent decades. As rapid industrialisation and urbanisation releases numerous toxic compounds into natural water bodies, polluting both fresh water resources as well as marine water. This process is focused on destroying or immobilizing toxic waste materials present in these water sources. Several techniques have been proposed for efficient wastewater treatment, most of them presenting some limitations, such as poor capacity, the generation of waste products, incomplete mineralisation and a high operating cost. The bioremediation of waste waters can be divided into two broad categories: *In-situ* and *Ex-situ* treatment. Both methods have significant advantages and disadvantages. The bioremediation process for different waste waters is discussed in this paper in brief.

KEYWORDS: Bioremediation, Treatment, Contamination, Microorganisms, Probiotics

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INTRODUCTION

Bioremediation is defined as the process whereby organic wastes are biologically degraded under controlled conditions. Bioremediation technology using microorganisms was invented by George M. Robinson.

By definition, bioremediation is the use of living organisms, primarily microorganisms, to degrade the environmental contaminants into less toxic forms. It uses naturally occurring bacteria and fungi or plants to degrade or detoxify substances hazardous to human health and/or the environment. The microorganisms may be indigenous to a contaminated area or they may be isolated from elsewhere and brought to the contaminated site (Okonko, *et al.*, 2007)

Not all contaminants are easily treated by bioremediation using microorganisms. For example, heavy metals such as cadmium and lead are not readily absorbed or captured by organisms. The assimilation of metals such as mercury into the food chain may worsen matters. Phyto-remediation is useful in these circumstances, because natural plants or transgenic plants are able to bio-accumulate these toxins, which are then harvested for removal. The heavy metal in the harvested biomass may further concentrated by incineration or even recycled for industrial use (Venkateswara Rao, 2008).

For effective bioremediation, the microorganisms must enzymatically attack the pollutants and convert them to harmless products. As bioremediation can be effective only where environmental conditions permit microbial growth and activity, its application often involves the manipulation of environmental parameters to allow microbial growth and degradation to proceed at a faster rate (Vidali, 2001).

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BIOREMEDIATION STRATEGIES

Different techniques are employed depending on the degree of saturation and aeration of an area.

- 1) *In-situ* techniques
- 2) *Ex-situ* techniques

1. *In situ* techniques

In-situ techniques are defined as those that are applied to soil and groundwater at the site with minimal disturbance. These techniques are generally the most desirable options due to lower cost and fewer disturbances, since they provide the treatment in place avoiding excavation and transport of contaminants. Treatment is limited by the depth of the soil that can be effectively treated. In many soils effective oxygen diffusion for desirable rates of bioremediation extend to a range of only a few cm to about 30 cm into the soil, although depths of 60 cm and greater have been effectively treated in some cases (Boopathy. 2000).

The most important land treatments are:

Bioventing

Bioventing is the most common *in situ* treatment and involves supplying air and nutrients through wells to contaminated soil to stimulate the indigenous bacteria. Bioventing employs low air flow rates and provides only the amount of oxygen necessary for the biodegradation while minimizing volatilization and release of contaminants to the atmosphere. It works for simple hydrocarbons and can be used where the contamination is deep under the surface (Pamela *et al.*, 2010).

Biosparging

Biosparging involves the injection of air under pressure below the water table to increase groundwater oxygen concentrations and enhance the rate of biological degradation of contaminants by naturally occurring bacteria. Biosparging increases the mixing in the saturated zone and thereby increases the contact between soil and groundwater. The ease and low cost of installing small-diameter air injection points allows considerable flexibility in the design and construction of the system (Antony *et al.*, 2006).

Bioaugmentation

Bioremediation frequently involves the addition of microorganisms indigenous or exogenous to the contaminated sites (Anjaneyulu Y *et al.*, 2005). Two factors limit the use of added microbial cultures in a land treatment unit:

- 1) Non indigenous cultures rarely compete well enough with an indigenous population to develop and sustain useful population levels .
- 2) Most soils with long-term exposure to biodegradable waste have indigenous microorganisms that are effective degraders if the land treatment unit is well managed.

Phytoremediation

Phytoremediation is a bioremediation process that uses various types of plants to remove, transfer, stabilize, and/or destroy contaminants in the soil and ground water.

2). *Ex-situ* techniques

Ex-situ techniques are those that are applied to soil and groundwater at the site which has been removed from the site via excavation (soil) or pumping (water). These techniques involve the excavation or removal of contaminated soil from ground (Paniagua-Michel. 2003).

Land farming

Land farming is a simple technique in which contaminated soil is excavated and spread over a prepared bed and periodically tilled until pollutants are degraded. The goal is to stimulate indigenous bio-degradative microorganisms and facilitate their aerobic degradation of contaminants. In general, the practice is limited to the treatment of superficial 10–35 cm of soil. Since land farming has the potential to reduce monitoring and

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maintenance costs, as well as clean-up liabilities, it has received much attention as a disposal alternative (Thassitou 2001).

Composting

Composting is a technique that involves combining contaminated soil with nonhazardous organic amendments such as manure or agricultural wastes. The presence of these organic materials supports the development of a rich microbial population and elevated temperature characteristic of composting. (Vidali, 2001).

Biopiles

Biopiles are a hybrid of land farming and composting. Essentially, engineered cells are constructed as aerated composted piles. Typically used for treatment of surface contamination with petroleum hydrocarbons they are a refined version of land farming that tend to control physical losses of the contaminants by leaching and volatilization. Biopiles provide a favorable environment for indigenous aerobic and anaerobic microorganisms (Asano, *et al.*, 2007).

Bioreactors

Slurry reactors or aqueous reactors are used for *ex-situ* treatment of contaminated soil and water pumped up from a contaminated plume. Bioremediation in reactors involves the processing of contaminated solid material (soil, sediment, sludge) or water through an engineered containment system. A slurry bioreactor may be defined as a containment vessel and apparatus used to create a three-phase (solid, liquid, and gas) mixing condition to increase the bioremediation rate of soil bound and water-soluble pollutants as a water slurry of the contaminated soil and biomass (usually indigenous microorganisms) capable of degrading target contaminants (Ruenglerpanyakul, 2004). In general, the rate and extent of biodegradation are greater in a bioreactor system than *in-situ* or in solid-phase systems because the contained environment is more manageable and hence more controllable and predictable.

MICROBIAL POPULATIONS FOR BIOREMEDIATION PROCESSES

Microorganisms can be isolated from almost any environmental conditions. Microbes will adapt and grow at sub zero temperatures, as well as extreme heat, desert conditions, in water, with an excess of oxygen, and in anaerobic conditions, with the presence of hazardous compounds or on any waste stream. The main requirements are an energy source and a carbon source. Because of the adaptability of microbes and other biological systems, these can be used to degrade or remediate environmental hazards (Loredana 2010).

We can subdivide these microorganisms into the following groups.

Aerobic

In the presence of oxygen, the aerobic bacteria such as *Pseudomonas*, *Alcaligenes*, *Sphingomonas*, *Rhodococcus*, and *Mycobacterium* are capable of degrading pollutants. These microbes degrade pesticides and hydrocarbons, both alkanes and polyaromatic compounds. Many of these bacteria use the contaminant as the sole source of carbon and energy (Boricha, H *et al.*, 2009).

Anaerobic

In the absence of oxygen, anaerobic bacteria are not as frequently used as aerobic bacteria. There is an increasing interest in anaerobic bacteria used for bioremediation of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) in river sediments, dechlorination of the solvent trichloroethylene (TCE) and chloroform (Derek, 1995).

Ligninolytic fungi

Fungi such as the white rot fungus *Phanaerochaete chrysosporium* have the ability to degrade an extremely diverse range of persistent or toxic environmental pollutants. Common substrates used include straw, saw dust, or corn cobs (Judith 2004).

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Methylotrophs

Aerobic bacteria utilize methane for carbon and energy. The initial enzyme in the pathway for aerobic degradation, methane monooxygenase, has a broad substrate range and is active against a wide range of compounds, including the chlorinated aliphatics trichloroethylene and 1,2-dichloroethane (Endong *et al.*, 2008).

BIOREMEDIATION OF AQUACULTURE WASTE WATERS

Aquaculture is the world's fastest growing food production sector (Moriarty, 1999). It was once considered an environmentally sound practice because of its traditional polyculture and integrated systems of farming based on optimum utilization of farm resources, including farm wastes. Increased production is being achieved by the expansion of land and water under culture and the use of more intensive and modern farming technologies that involve higher usage of inputs such as water, feeds, fertilizers and chemicals. As a result, aquaculture is now considered as a potential polluter of the aquatic environment (Pillay, 1992).

Waste Production in Aquaculture

The wastes in hatcheries or aquaculture farms can be categorized as: (1) residual food and faecal matter; (2) metabolic by-products; (3) residues of biocides and biostats; (4) fertilizer derived wastes; (5) wastes produced during moulting; and (6) collapsing algal blooms (Sharma and Scheeno, 1999).

The current approach to improving water quality in aquaculture is the application of microbes/enzymes to the ponds, known as bioremediation. The use of bioremediators results in a lower accumulation of slime or organic matter in the pond bottom, better penetration of oxygen into the sediment and a generally better environment for the farmed stock. A successful bioremediation involves:

- 1) Optimizing nitrification rates to keep low ammonia concentration
- 2) Optimizing denitrification rates to eliminate excess nitrogen from ponds as nitrogen gas
- 3) Maximizing sulphide oxidation to reduce accumulation of hydrogen sulphide
- 4) Maximizing carbon mineralization to carbon dioxide to minimize sludge Accumulation
- 5) Maximizing primary productivity that stimulates shrimp production and also secondary crops
- 6) Maintaining a diverse and stable pond community where undesirable species do not become dominant.

Bioremediation of Organic Detritus

The dissolved and suspended organic matter contains mainly carbon chains and is highly available to microbes and algae. A good bioremediator must contain microbes that are capable of effectively clearing carbonaceous wastes from water. Members of the genus *Bacillus*, like *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus licheniformis*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus coagulans*, and of the genus *Phenibacillus*, like *Phenibacillus polymyxa*, are good examples of bacteria suitable for bioremediation of organic detritus. However, these are not normally present in the required amounts in the water column, their natural habitat being the sediment. When certain *Bacillus* strains are added to the water in sufficient quantities, they can make an impact. They compete with the bacterial flora naturally present for the available organic matter, like leached or excess feed and shrimp faeces (Sharma, 1999). As a part of bio-augmentation, the *Bacillus* can be produced, mixed with sand or clay and broadcasted to be deposited in the pond bottom (Singh *et al.*, 2001). *Lactobacillus* is also used along with *Bacillus* to break down the organic detritus. These bacteria produce a variety of enzymes that break down proteins and starch to small molecules, which are then taken up as energy sources by other organisms. The removal of large organic compounds reduces water turbidity (Haug, 2003).

Bioremediation of Nitrogenous Compounds

Nitrogen applications in excess of pond assimilatory capacity can lead to deterioration of water quality through the accumulation of nitrogenous compounds (e.g., ammonia and nitrite) with toxicity to fish and shrimp. The principal sources of ammonia are fish excretion and sediment flux derived from the mineralization of organic matter and molecular diffusion from reduced sediment, although cyanobacterial nitrogen fixation and atmospheric deposition are occasionally important (Ayyappan and Mishra, 2003).

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Nitrification process as follows:

Bacteriological nitrification is the most practical method for the removal of ammonia from closed aquaculture systems and it is commonly achieved by setting of sand and gravel bio-filter through which water is allowed to circulate. The ammonia oxidizers are placed under five genera, *Nitrosomonas*, *Nitrosovibrio*, *Nitrosococcus*, *Nitrolobus* and *Nitrospira*, and nitrite oxidisers under three genera, *Nitrobacter*, *Nitrococcus* and *Nitrospira*. There are also some heterotrophic nitrifiers that produce only low levels of nitrite and nitrate and often use organic sources of nitrogen rather than ammonia or nitrite. Nitrification not only produces nitrate but also alters the pH slightly towards the acidic range, facilitating the availability of soluble materials (Ayyappan and Mishra, 2003).

The vast majority of aquaculture ponds accumulate nitrate, as they do not contain a denitrifying filter. Denitrifying filters help to convert nitrate to nitrogen. It creates an anaerobic region where anaerobic bacteria can grow and reduce nitrate to nitrogen gas (Rao, 2002). Nitrate may follow several biochemical pathways following production by nitrification.

Unlike the limited species diversity of bacteria mediating nitrification, at least 14 genera of bacteria can reduce nitrate. Among these, *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus* and *Alkaligenes* are the most prominent numerically (Focht and Verstraete, 1977).

Recently, (Andre Nduwimana & others 2009) demonstrated the bioremediation of aquaculture discharge using a combination of Nitrobacteria culture solution and grass plant species, *Lotium perenne* as a biofilter to improve waste water quality.

Bioremediation of Hydrogen Sulphide

Sulphur is of some interest in aquaculture because of its importance in anoxic sediments. In aerobic conditions, organic sulphur decomposes to sulphide, which in turn gets oxidised to sulphate. Sulphate is highly soluble in water and so gradually disperses from sediments. Sulphide oxidation is mediated by micro organisms in the sediment. Under anaerobic conditions, sulphate may be used in place of oxygen in microbial metabolism. This process leads to the production of hydrogen sulphide gas (Midlen *et al.* 1998). The H₂S is produced by a series of microbially mediated reductions (Boyd, 1995).

Organic loading can stimulate H₂S production and reduction in the diversity of benthic fauna (Mattson and Linden, 1983). H₂S is soluble in water and has been suggested as the cause of gill damage and other ailments in fish (Beveridge, 1987). Un-ionised H₂S is extremely toxic to fish at concentrations that may occur in natural waters as well as in aquaculture farms (Bonn and Follis, 1967). Bioassays of several species of fish suggest that any detectable concentration of H₂S should be considered detrimental to fish production (Boyd, 1979).

The photosynthetic benthic bacteria that break H₂S at pond bottom have been widely used in aquaculture to maintain a favourable environment (Singh and Radhika, 2001). These bacteria contain bacterio-chlorophyll that absorb light and perform photosynthesis under anaerobic conditions (Haug, 2003). They are purple and green sulphur bacteria that grow at the anaerobic portion of the sediment-water interface. Photosynthetic purple non-sulphur bacteria can decompose organic matter, H₂S, NO₂ and harmful wastes of ponds. The purple and green sulphur bacteria obtain reducing electrons from H₂S at a lower energy cost than H₂O splitting photo-autotrophs

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and thus require lower light intensities for carrying out photosynthesis. The general equation of this reaction is as follows:

The family Rhodospirillaceae can be used as efficient mineralizers at pond bottom as they grow in both aerobic and anaerobic conditions as heterotrophic bacteria even in the dark without utilizing solar energy (Singh and Radhika, 2001). The importance Photosynthetic bacteria in aquaculture are *Rhodospirillum*, *Rhodopseudomonas*, *Rhodomicrobium*, *Chromatium*, *Thiocystis*, *Thiosarcina*, *Thiospirillum*, *Thiocapsa*, *Lamprocystis*, *Thiodictyon*, *Thiopedia*, *Amoebobacter*, *Ectothiorhodospira*, *Chlorobium*, *Prosthecochloris*, *Chloropseudomonas*, *Pelodictyon*, *Clathrochloris* (Haung, 2003).

Bioremediators as Disease Controlling Agents

Most probiotics proposed as biological control agents in aquaculture belong to the Lactic Acid Bacteria (*Lactobacillus*, *Carnobacterium* etc.), *Vibrio* (*V. alginolyticus*), *Bacillus*, and *Pseudomonas* (Singh *et al.*, 2001). Beneficial microbes, such as non-pathogenic isolates of *V.alginolyticus*, can be inoculated into shrimp culture systems to suppress the pathogenic vibrios like *V.harveyi*, *V. parahaemolyticus* and *V. splendens* and reduce the opportunistic invasion of these pathogens in shrimps (Jameson, 2003). - Table 1.

Table 1. Microorganisms used as bioremediators

Identity of the bioremediator	Source	Used on	Method of application	References
Gram-Positive Bacteria				
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. 48	Common snook	<i>Centropomus undecimalis</i>	Added to water; reduced salinity	Kennedy <i>et al.</i> , 1998
<i>Bacillus</i> sp	Commercial product	Penaeids	Water	Moriarty, 1998
<i>Bacillus</i> sp	Commercial product	Channel catfish	Spread in pond water	Queiroz and Boyd, 1998
Mixed culture, mostly <i>Bacillus</i> sp.	Commercial product	<i>Brachionus plicatilis</i>	Mixed with water	Hirata <i>et al.</i> , 1998
Gram-Negative Bacteria				
<i>Aeromonas media</i>	Unknown	<i>Crassostrea gigas</i>	Mixed with water	Gibson <i>et al.</i> , 1998
<i>Aeromonas</i> CA2	Unknown	<i>Crassostrea gigas</i>	Mixed with water	Douillet and Langdon, 1994
<i>Photobacterium</i> sp.	Unknown	<i>Penaeus chinensis</i>	Mixed with water	Xu-per communication, 1997
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescence</i>	<i>Onchorhynchus mykiss</i>	<i>Onchorhynchus mykiss</i>	Mixed with water to 105 or 106 cells ml ⁻¹	Gram <i>et al.</i> , 2001
<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp.	<i>Onchorhynchus mykiss</i>	<i>Onchorhynchus mykiss</i>	Mixed in water	Spanggaard <i>et al.</i> ,2001
<i>Roseobacter</i> sp. BS 107	Unknown	Scallop larvae	Mixed in water	Ruiz-Ponte <i>et al.</i> ,1999

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Probiotics in Aquaculture Bioremediation

The newest attempt being made to improve water quality in aquaculture is the application of probiotics and/or enzymes to the ponds, which involves manipulation of microorganisms in ponds to enhance mineralization of organic matter and get rid of undesirable waste compounds (Akpor *et al.*, 2010) - Table 2.

Table 2. PROBIOTICS AND THEIR ROLE

<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	Mineralization and Breakage of proteins
<i>Nitrosomonas sp.</i>	Oxidation of ammonia
<i>Nitrobacter sp.</i>	Oxidation of nitrites
<i>Aerobacter sp.</i>	Reduction of organic matter
<i>Cellulomonas sp.</i>	Breakage of plant material

(Akpor O. B. *et al.*, 2010).

BIOREMEDIATION OF INDUSTRIAL WASTE WATERS

The principal characteristics of industrial wastewater are its solids content, colour, odour, temperature, organic and inorganic constituents. Colour is a qualitative characteristic that can be used to assess the general condition of wastewater. Wastewater that is light brown in colour is less than 6 h old, while a light-to-medium grey colour is characteristic of wastewaters that have undergone some degree of decomposition or that have been in the collection system for some time. Lastly, if the colour is dark grey or black, the wastewater is typically septic, having undergone extensive bacterial decomposition under anaerobic conditions. The blackening of wastewater is often due to the formation of various sulphides, particularly, ferrous sulphide.

The principal odorous compound is hydrogen sulphide. Other compounds, such as indol, skatol, cadaverin and mercaptan, formed under anaerobic conditions or present in the effluents of pulp and paper mills (hydrogen sulphide, mercaptan, dimethylsulphide etc.), may also cause a rather offensive odour (Asamudo *et al.*, 2005).

Several industries discharge heavy metals. Chromium is the most widely used and discharged to the environment from different sources. The pollutant cadmium in water may arise from industrial discharges and mining wastes. Cyanide ion, CN⁻, is probably the most important of the various inorganic species in wastewater. Different colouring agents like dyes, inorganic pigments, tannins, lignins etc usually impart colour. More than 8000 chemically different types of dyes are currently manufactured and the biggest consumers of these dyes are the textile industries (Rajgopalan, 1995), paper and pulp industries (Ali and Srikrishnan, 2001), dye and dye intermediates industries, pharmaceutical industries (Koplin *et al.*, 2000), tannery (Routh, 1998) and Kraft bleaching industries which are probably the most potential contributors as far as colour pollution is concerned. These industries consume large quantities of water and are therefore a source of considerable colour pollution. Colour is contributed by phenolic compounds such as tannins, lignins (2–3%) and organic colourants (3–4%) (Clarke & Steinle, 1995) and with a maximum contribution from dye and dye intermediates, which could be sulphur/mordant/reactive/cationic/dispersed/azo/acid/vat dye (Raghavacharya, 1997). These dyes are difficult to be decolourized due to their complex structure, synthetic origin and recalcitrant nature.

The ability of biological treatment process for decolourization of industrial effluents is ambiguous, different and divergent. Observations indicate that dyes themselves are not biologically degradable since microorganisms do not utilize the colour constituents as a source of food. Most currently used laboratory methods for biodegradation involve aerobic microorganisms, which utilize molecular oxygen as reducing equivalent acceptor during the respiration process.

BIOREMEDIATION OF OIL

Many microorganisms possess the enzymatic capability to degrade petroleum hydrocarbons. Some microorganisms degrade alkanes, others aromatics, and others both paraffinic and aromatic hydrocarbons. Often the normal alkanes in the range C₁₀ to C₂₆ are viewed as the most readily degraded, but low-molecular-weight

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aromatics, such as benzene, toluene and xylene, which are among the toxic compounds found in petroleum, are also very readily biodegraded by many marine microorganisms. More complex structures are more resistant to biodegradation, meaning that fewer microorganisms can degrade those structures and the rates of biodegradation are lower than biodegradation rates of the simpler hydrocarbon structures found in petroleum (Bourne Jr., 2007).

Oil degrading microbes

The biodegradation of petroleum in the marine environment is carried out largely by diverse bacterial populations, including various *Pseudomonas* species. The hydrocarbon-biodegrading populations are widely distributed in the world's oceans. Generally, in pristine environments, the hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria comprise < 1% of the total bacterial population. These bacteria presumably utilize hydrocarbons that are naturally produced by plants, algae, and other living organisms. They also utilize other substrates, such as carbohydrates and proteins. When an environment is contaminated with petroleum, the proportion of hydrocarbon-degrading microorganisms increases rapidly. In particular, in marine environments contaminated with hydrocarbons, there is an increase in the proportion of bacterial populations with plasmids containing genes for hydrocarbon utilization. (Atlas, 1995). The efficient oil degrading marine Cyanobacteria are *Oscillatoria salina*, *Plectonema terebrans* and *Aphanocapsa* sp. (Raghukumar *et al.*, 2004).

BIOREMEDIATION OF MUNICIPAL AND SEWAGE WASTE WATERS

Municipal wastewater is mainly comprised of water (99.9%) together with relatively small concentrations of suspended and dissolved organic and inorganic solids. Among the organic substances present in sewage are carbohydrates, lignin, fats, soaps, synthetic detergents, proteins and their decomposition products, as well as various natural and synthetic organic chemicals from the process industries. Municipal wastewater also contains a variety of inorganic substances from domestic and industrial sources including a number of potentially toxic elements such as arsenic, cadmium, chromium, copper, lead, mercury, zinc, etc (Endong *et al.*, 2008).

Presently, the activated sludge system is the most widely used biological treatment process for both domestic and sewage wastewaters. The system is a biological method that is performed by a mixed community of microbes and uses the metabolic reactions of the microbes to produce high-quality effluent in an aquatic environment. The major microorganisms found in wastewater influents are viruses, bacteria, fungi, protozoa and nematodes. The constant aeration, agitation and recirculation in an activated sludge system create an ideal environment for the numerous microorganisms present, while inhibiting the growth of larger organisms. Bacteria, fungi, rotifers, viruses, nematodes and protozoa are commonly found in the activated sludge. The species of microorganisms that dominate a system depends on environmental conditions, process design and the mode of plant operation. This will help to ensure science-based decisions with respect to effluent standards and limitations, as set by regulatory bodies and a clearer understanding (Akpor and Muchie, 2010).

The commercial bioremediator, *Bioclean*[®] STP is available in dry concentrate bacterial formulations, specially designed to provide improved waste degradation in sewage treatment. Each gram of the product contains up to 4 billion microbes. There are up to 58 different strains of bacteria in each gram of *Bioclean*[®] STP product, which can biodegrade very diverse types of molecules. It has been used in compact Bio-engineered Decentralized Sewage Treatment Plants with astounding success. Discharge water of BOD of 6 ppm is achieved in these plants, while the operational cost is half that of conventional plants. In most cases the water is recycled.

Microbial mat in metal and radionuclide removal

Microbial mats sequester heavy metals, metalloids, radionuclides and oxyanions. The microbial mats removed manganese in ponds receiving drainage from an abandoned coal mine in Alabama, after pH neutralization (Phillips *et al.*, 1995). Other concentration of metals was also removed by mats. Metals such as lead and iron were also reduced by microbial mat in the drainage system (Phillips and Bender, 1998).

Microalgae in an Integrated Aquaculture System

Portuguese researchers investigated the potential to use microalgae to process fish-farm effluents (primarily inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus) in seawater and use the microalgae as food for the *Tapes decussates* bivalve

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clam. The nutrient removal efficiency for ammonium and nitrite-nitrogen was in the range of 80%-100%, for nitrate 41%-100%, and for phosphorus 21- 99%. After treatment, the water is similar in quality to fresh seawater. Researchers note the importance of this process, since fish farm effluent nutrient levels are generally too low for removal using standard bacterial systems. (Borges *et al.*, 2005).

Micro Algae in Municipal Waste Water Treatment

Municipal wastewater is usually treated to get rid of undesirable substances by subjecting the organic matter to biodegradation by microorganisms such as bacteria. The biodegradation involves the degradation of organic matter to smaller molecules (CO₂, NH₃, PO₄ etc.), and requires constant supply of oxygen. The process of supplying oxygen is expensive, tedious, and requires a lot of expertise and manpower. These problems are overcome by growing microalgae in the ponds and tanks where wastewater treatment is carried out. The algae release the O₂ while carrying out the photosynthesis which ensures a continuous supply of oxygen for biodegradation. Algae - based municipal wastewater treatment systems are mainly used for nutrient removal (removal of nitrogen and phosphorus). The added benefit is the resulting biomass that can be used as biofuel feedstock. According to (Rose *et al.*, 2002) a pH of 9.2 for 24 hours will provide a 100% kill of *E. coli* and most pathogenic bacteria and viruses. (Pahad and Rao 1962) also found that *E. coli* could not grow in wastewater with a pH higher than 9.2.

Micro algae in industrial waste water treatment

Industrial wastewaters are extremely varied and the microorganisms employed to treat these industrial wastewaters also vary accordingly. Biomass immobilization is an efficient means of retaining biomass during WWT (Nicollella *et al.*, 2000) and microalgae immobilization in polymeric material such as carrageenan, chitosan, or alginate has been reported by various authors (Chevalier and De la Noue, 1985; Lau *et al.*, 1995; Robinson *et al.*, 1998).

BIOREMEDIATION VIA MOLECULAR ENGINEERING

The bioremediation of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) using genetically modified microorganisms has become a rapidly growing area of research for environmental protection. These are mainly used in 3 major classes of POPs, PAHs, PCBs, and pesticides. (Ang *et al.*, 2005). The rapid advancement of molecular biological methods has facilitated the study of microbial community structure without bias introduced by cultivation. It is expected to provide new insights into process optimization, validation and the impact on the existing ecosystem.

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF BIOREMEDIATION

Advantages

Bioremediation is a natural process and is therefore perceived by the public as an acceptable waste treatment process for contaminated water. The residues for the treatment are usually harmless products and include carbon dioxide, water, and cell biomass.

Theoretically, bioremediation is useful for the complete destruction of a wide variety of contaminants. Many compounds that are legally considered to be hazardous can be transformed to harmless products. This eliminates the chance of future liability associated with treatment and disposal of contaminated material.

Instead of transferring contaminants from one environmental medium to another, for example, from land to water or air, the complete destruction of target pollutants is possible.

Bioremediation can often be carried out on site, often without causing a major disruption of normal activities. This also eliminates the need to transport quantities of waste off site and the potential threats to human health and the environment that can arise during transportation.

Bioremediation can prove less expensive than other technologies that are used for clean-up of hazardous waste.

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Disadvantages

Bioremediation is limited to those compounds that are biodegradable. Not all compounds are susceptible to rapid and complete degradation.

There are some concerns that the products of biodegradation may be more persistent or toxic than the parent compound.

Biological processes are often highly specific. Important site factors required for success include the presence of metabolically capable microbial populations, suitable environmental growth conditions, and appropriate levels of nutrients and contaminants.

It is difficult to extrapolate from bench and pilot-scale studies to full-scale field operations.

Research is needed to develop and engineer bioremediation technologies that are appropriate for sites with complex mixtures of contaminants that are not evenly dispersed in the environment. Contaminants may be present as solids, liquids, and gases.

Bioremediation often takes longer than other treatment options, such as excavation and removal of soil or incineration.

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CONCLUSION

Bioremediation is a technological tool that holds great value for the future as scientist learns more about its capabilities, it is likely to become one of the best technologies used to clean up and protect our environment.

REFERENCES

Akpor O. B. and Muchie M., (2010). Bioremediation of polluted wastewater influent: Phosphorus and nitrogen removal. *Scientific Research and Essays Volume*. 5(21), pp. 3222-3230.

Anjaneyulu Y., Sreedhara Chary, N., Samuel Suman Raj, D., (2005). Decolourization of industrial effluents – available methods and emerging technologies – a review, *Reviews in Environmental Science and Bio/Technology*, 4:245–273.

Antony and R. Philip .S.P., (2006). Bioremediation in Shrimp Culture Systems, NAGA, *World Fish Center Quarterly*, Volume. 29 (3 &4).

Antony, S.P. and Philip. R., (2006). Bioremediation of shrimp culture systems, NAGA World Fish Centre, 29: (3 & 4).

Asamudo, N. U., Dava, A.S. and Ezeronye, O.U., (2005). Bioremediation of textile effluent using *Phanerochaete chrysosporium*, *African Journal of Biotechnology* Volume. 4 (13), pp. 1548-1553.

Asano, T., Burton, F. L., Leverenz, H. L., Tsuchihashi, R., and Tchobanoglous, G., (2007). Water Reuse, Issues, Technologies, and Applications, Metcalf & Eddy | AECOM.

Boopathy, R., (2000). Factors limiting bioremediation technologies. *Bio resource Technology* 74 :63-67.

Borges, M. T., Silva, P., Moreira, L., and Soares, R. (2005). Integration of consumer-targeted microalgal production with marine fish effluent biofiltration—a strategy for mariculture sustainability. *Journal of Applied Phycology*, 17(3): 187-197.

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Boricha, H. and Fulekar M.H., (2009). *Pseudomonas plecoglossicida* as a novel organism for the bioremediation of cypermethrin. *Biology and Medicine*, 4: 1-10.

Bourne, J. K., Jr., (2007). Biofuels: Boon or Boondoggle? *National Geographic*, 38-59.

Derek R. Lovley, (1995). Bioremediation of organic and metal contaminants with dissimilatory metal reduction. *Journal of Industrial Microbiology*, 14: 85-90.

Endong Zhang *et al.*, (2008), Ammonia- Nitrogen and Orthophosphate removal by immobilized *Scenedesmus* sp., isolated from municipal waste water for potential use in tertiary treatment. *Biosource Technology* 99: 3787 – 3793.

Judith Bender, Peter Phillips, (2004). Microbial mats for multiple applications in aquaculture and bioremediation. *Bioresource Technology*, 94: 229–238.

Kelly A. Reynolds, (2002). Bioremediation: Using microbes to clean up hazardous waste, Volume 44, Number 9.

Loredana Stabili, Roberto schirosi, Margharita Icciano, Emanuela Mola and Adriana Gianfranco, (2010). Bioremediation of bacteria in aquaculture waste using the polychaete *Sabella spallanzanii*, *New Biotechnology*, Volume 00, Number 00, July.

Marinho-Soriano.E., (2009). Nutrients removal from aquaculture wastewater using the macroalgae *Gracilaria birdiae*, *Biomass and Bio energy*, 33: 327 -331.

Marinho-Soriano.E., (2009). Evaluation of *Gracilaria caudata* J. Agardh for bioremediation of nutrients from shrimp farming wastewater. *Bio resource Technology*, 100: 6192–6198.

Okonko, I. O. and Shittu, O. B., (2007). Bioremediation of wastewater and municipal water treatment using latex exudate from *Calotropis procera* (sodom apple), *Electronic journal of Environmental, Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 6 (3): 1890-1904.

Pamela Chavez- Crooker and Johanna Obreque-Contreras, (2010). Bioremediation of aquaculture wastes. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, 21: 313–317.

Pandey, R.S. and Upadhyay. B.V., (2010). *Pseudomonas fluorescens* can be used for bioremediation of textile effluent Direct Orange-102. *Tropical Ecology* 51(2): 397-403.

Paniagua-Michel.J., Garcia.O., (2003). Ex-situ bioremediation of shrimp culture effluent using constructed microbial mats. *Aquacultural Engineering* 28: 131-139.

Ruenglertpanyakul. W., Attasat S. and Wanichpongpan .P., (2004). Nutrient removal from shrimp farm effluent by aquatic plants. *Water Science and Technology*, Vol 50 No 6, pp 321 -330. IWA publishing.

Thassitou P.K and I.S. Arvanitoyannis, (2001). Bioremediation: a novel approach to food waste Management. *Trends in Food Science & Technology* 12: 185–196.

Venkateswara rao.A., (2008). Bioremediation – an advanced strategy to restore the health of aquaculture pond ecosystem, *Technical Articles – Aquaculture*.

Vidali.M., (2001). Bioremediation. An overview, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, Vol. 73, No. 7, pp. 1163–1172.

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